

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ATTITUDE TOWARDS BIOLOGY AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN BIOLOGY AMONG SIGHTED AND VISUALLY IMPAIRED STUDENTS OF CLASS IX AT VARANASI CITY

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Abstract

This is a comparative study between the sighted and visually impaired students regarding their attitude towards biology and academic achievement in Biology. To taste the objectives of study researcher made hypotheses that there is no significant difference in the attitude towards Biology between sighted and visually impaired students towards biology, and there is no significant difference in the academic achievement between sighted and visually impaired students in biology. After data analysis both the hypotheses were rejected. Result clearly shows that there is significant difference in the attitude and academic achievement between both the groups. Researcher found that sighted student has more positive attitude towards biology as well as more academic achievement in Biology than the visually impaired students. This clearly reveals that the attitude towards Biology affects the academic achievement in Biology. Thus, this study suggest that teacher of biology should try to develop more positive attitude in visually impaired students towards Biology to improve their Academic achievement in Biology. This study had limitation due to small sample size which can generalize only with considerable risk.

Keywords: *Attitude towards Biology, Academic Achievement, Sighted Students, visually impaired students.*

The Kothari Commission (1964–66), the first education commission of independent India, observed: “the education of the handicapped children should be an inseparable part of the education system. There are so many fields of education like physics, social science, mathematics etc. Each field of education has its importance. Among them science is also play

a significant role in formation of strong base for individual and social development with global scientific and technological growth occurring rapidly, declining student interest in science courses and careers is a worldwide concern that has prompted science education reform efforts on an international scale. Since student attitudes toward science effect course and career choices, measuring the impact of reform efforts on student attitudes is important and will require measurement tools with robust psychometric properties (Owen et al, 2008). As science has become ever more deeply embedded in our everyday life, how ordinary people perceive science has attracted growing attention not only from the scientific community, but also from social scientists (Bak, 2001). Biology is a branch of science, which deals with the study of living organisms, which are immeasurable diverse and complex than the non- living matter. Hence, biology is also described as life science or natural science. So the objectives of teaching biology are similar to the objective of science.

The achievement in any subject directly or indirectly affected by several factors like mental or physical condition of the students, and other personality aspects. Attitude towards subjects may also affect the academic achievement. Several studies show that attitude affects achievement at certain degree. There is so many research conducted on the attitude and its effect on achievement in different subjects. Study of Darchingpuri (1989) show significant relationship between scores on scientific attitude and achievement in science, another study of Rao, D.B (1990) found scientific attitude and achievement at average value but there was a positive relationship among attitude and achievement. Kar, D. K (1990) observe that distribution of attitude score was negatively skewed, boy were forced to be more favourable disposed towards science then girl and there was positive relationship between attitude and achievement. Maikhuri & Pandey (1997) obtain significant difference in the academic achievement of the high and low self-concept. Result of E.Lynn Talton. Ronald D. Simpson (2006) indicated: (1) student attitudes towards the class room environment predicted between 56 to 61 % of the variance in attitude towards science, (2) student attitude towards the classroom environment predicted between 5 to 14 % of the variance in achievement in science. (3) Student attitude towards science and attitude towards the classroom environment predicted between 8 and 18 % of the variance in achievements. Though sufficient literature is available on academic achievement in science related to various variables for the sighted students but there is lack of study in biology as well as for visually impaired students, therefore comparative analysis of the academic achievement of sighted and visually impaired student with reference

to their attitude towards biology had been done and helps us to understand the how attitude towards biology affect the achievement.

There were two objectives of the study: -

- (1) To compare the attitude of sighted and visually impaired students towards biology, and
- (2) To compare the academic achievement of sighted and visually impaired students.

So, we made two null hypotheses: -

- (1) There is no significant difference between the attitudes of sighted and visually impaired students, and
- (2) There is no significant difference between the academic achievement between the sighted and visually impaired students.

There were 60 Participant who were 60 student of class VIII. Among them 30 were sighted students (15 boys and 15 girls) and 30 were visually impaired students (15 boys and 15 girls).

There are two tools used in this study:

- (1) Attitude inventory
- (2) Achievement test.

Attitude inventory contains 28 items, scored in reverse fashion assigning 4,3,2,1,0 to Strongly agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral (N), Disagree (D) and Strong disagree (SD) For positive items and 0,1,2,3,4 for negative items. Achievement test contains 30 items.

Investigator had to approach the authorities of several schools in order to ask for permission to go through the tools. Firstly, Attitude inventory applied to students to know attitude towards biology there after applied academic achievement test to compare the students with low and high attitude towards Biology.

It is clear from statistical analysis there is a significant difference between the attitude towards biology of sighted and visually impaired students because value of 't' was 5.34 means significant at 0.05 level of significance. There is significant difference between the academic achievement of sighted and visually impaired students because of having 't' value 13.59 is much higher than the table value 2.05. So, both the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 1: Attitude towards biology of sighted and visually impaired students

Sample	N	M	S. D	Table value	t-value	Level of significance	Result
Sighted Students	30	75.66	4.80				Significant at 0.05 level
Visually Impaired Students	30	66.83	7.49	2.05	5.34	0.05	

Table 2: Academic achievement in biology of sighted and visually impaired students-

Sample	N	M	S. D	Table value	t-value	Level of significance	Result
Sighted Students	30	19.66	1.86				Significant at 0.05 level
Visually Impaired Students	30	16.66	1.74	2.05	13.59	0.05	

Findings clearly suggested that the sighted students have more positive attitude and high academic achievement than the visually impaired students. Almost all visually impaired students thought that biology is a very tough subject, they feel problem in attaining concept of biology due to lack of interest. So, their academic achievement in biology was very poor as comparison to sighted students who have much interest and positive attitude.

So, it clear that sighted and visually impaired students were not identical as far as their attitude towards biology and academic achievements were concerned.

This study may helpful in changing the teaching strategies for better attainment of concept of biology and teacher should try to know the reason why visually impaired student have low attitude toward biology. They should try to develop a positive attitude towards biology. They should improve classroom practice in order to make the classroom in a joyful place to learn. We suggest that broad and intensive study should be conduct using large sample. Researcher should also try to find out reason behind low attitude and should also find out techniques to develop high attitude toward biology.

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